

Modular programme for Education and Training

YOUTH SPORT COACH

M#3 Inclusive Coaching / Safeguarding

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Six Core Modules of EduPASS Modular Programme for Education and Training for Youth Sport Coach

The following are the proposed six core modules for Youth Sport Coaches education and training programmes that were developed as part of the EduPASS Erasmus+ Project. The core modules should be seen as a flexible reference point which require contextual adaptation. Those individuals and/or organisations using the six core modules to develop learning opportunities for Youth Sport Coaches should use the knowledge of their specific context to customise the modules to fit their needs, resources and objectives.

Each of the six EduPASS core modules proposed for YSC education and training programmes was developed building on the knowledge and insights, which can be found in the [European Coaching Children Curriculum \(ECCC\)](#). The ECCC, in turn, is built around the Primary Functions of the Coach as described in the European Sport Coaching Framework (2017) ([CoachLearn | European Sport Coaching Framework](#)) and the [International Sport Coaching Framework \(2013\)](#).

The respective module number and order in which the modules are presented in the table below do not indicate that modules must be introduced in this specific order, when implementing a Youth Sport Coach education and training programme. Rather the numbers simply serve as distinct denominators to help identify specific modules in the overall context of the EduPASS YSC education and training programme.

Core Module Overview

No	Module Title	Description
1	Daily Physical Activity and Sport & Motor Skills Assessment	<p>Daily physical activity, Movement, Play, and Sports (PAMPS) has many benefits for children – physically, psychologically, emotionally and cognitively. In this context, the development of physical literacy of each child is essential.</p> <p>Awareness of trends in children’s participation levels, physical activity guidelines, the needs and wants of children and how to engage with children in age-appropriate ways, will assist the coach.</p> <p>Knowledge on the growth and development of children in all aspects (socially, physically, emotionally and cognitively) is essential.</p> <p>This should be underpinned by the coach’s personal values and beliefs about the role of PAMPS for children and young people and about what constitutes ‘good practice’ (their coaching philosophy).</p> <p>To support individual children and to develop programmes based on their needs, the ability to assess motor skills will guide this work.</p>

<p>2</p>	<p>Principles of Coaching Children</p>	<p>The principles of good coaching practice with children should be used by the Youth Sport Coach (YSC). These form the basis for the 10 principles of the ICOACHKIDS Pledge:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Principle 1 — Be child-centred • Principle 2 — Be holistic • Principle 3 — Be inclusive • Principle 4 — Make it fun and safe • Principle 5 — Prioritise the love for sport over learning sport • Principle 6 — Focus on foundational skills • Principle 7 — Engage parents positively • Principle 8 — Plan progressive programmes • Principle 9 — Use difference methods to enhance learning • Principle 10 — Use competition in a developmental way <p>The YSC develops a programme based on their needs and the stage of development of children, based on the principles of coaching children.</p> <p>The YSC seeks to optimise the environment in which the programme occurs. The ability to navigate this can be guided by the Youth Sport Compass. The compass has 4 pillars – Developmental, Motivational, Caring and Social Safety – which can guide the YSC.</p> <p>The organisational and social context of the programme, including the participants (children/parents/club) should be taken into account.</p>
<p>3</p>	<p>Inclusive Coaching / Safeguarding</p>	<p>The Youth Sport Coach builds positive and effective relationships and works with a group of participants (children, club, school, parents, federation and other levels) and takes responsibility for the realisation of the common and individual objectives, and to achieve the programme and club goals. Hearing ‘the Voice’ of each child is an important component of this.</p> <p>Safeguarding and child protection must underpin the establishment of a safe environment for children in sport.</p>
<p>4</p>	<p>Fundamental Movement Skills and Play</p>	<p>Children should develop foundational motor skills to underpin their love of being active and to have the competence to engage in a range of activities. The development of fundamental movement (balance, agility, coordination, speed) and motor skills (run, move, jump, land, throw, catch, kick, etc) is essential, and is supported by contexts that engage children in fundamental play activities.</p>
<p>5</p>	<p>Hands-on Coaching</p>	<p>The Youth Sport Coach needs to develop their personal coaching skills and coaching tools. These include - introducing activities, demonstration, set-up and stand back, questioning and listening, feedback and reflection.</p> <p>Based on the principles of coaching children, inclusive coaching, and development of fundamental motor skills, the YSC needs to plan and organise suitable and challenging practices and attendance at events, using effective pedagogy and methodology, to promote the learning and improvement of children.</p>

		<p>The development of personal coaching skills and the planning of practices/events need to be practiced both with peers and in experiential learning situations with children. Thus, the aim of this module is to help craft safe learning experiences where “coaches learn how to coach by coaching”. Those hands-on coaching experiences enable coach learners to prepare coaching, engage in, and have an opportunity to receive feedback and engage in self-reflection about their coaching practice.</p>
<p>6</p>	<p>Plan, Reflect and Learn</p>	<p>The environment, which Youth Sport Coaches contribute to, can be welcoming and inclusive to all children. Individual coaches can provide this in their personal coaching and can also contribute to a club / school having child-centred values and policies. The Youth Sport Coach will examine their personal coaching philosophy and a means to support a club / school to adopt child-centred values and policies.</p> <p>Reflection on practice has been identified as a key means of learning and ongoing development for coaches. This can be supported by engaging with others and to a club / school being a learning environment for coaches (as well as children). Reflection is a learned skill and the Youth Sport Coach will reflect on their practice individually, with co-coaches and with a mentor.</p>

Youth Sport Coach – Programme Outcomes

The action-oriented outcomes and results for coaches for the complete module programme for Education and Training are presented below. The outcomes have been adapted from the [European Sport Coaching Framework](#) (Human Kinetics, 2017).

	The Youth Sport Coach in training will have taken the first steps towards being able to:
Coaching Vision and Strategy	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Develop a suitable vision for the programme relevant to the participants (and in line with institutional priorities) • Make effective and informed decisions relating to the planning, implementation, monitoring and evaluation of mid- to long-term programmes (of practice and competition) based on (institutional and) participant needs • Encourage adopting sustainable, life-long engagement in PAMPS / Daily PA
Shape the Environment	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Know how to identify, reflect on and challenge prevailing beliefs, values and assumptions within the coaching environment to establish a suitable culture for PAMPS • Know how to create an environment where all children feel safe and included • Know about and be able to identify potential dangers for children in sport • Contribute to crafting and upholding a coaching environment / club / school that has child-centred values and policies • Build a community of practice and contribute to the on-going learning of other coaches and that where they coach is a learning environment for coaches.
Building Positive Relationships	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Know how to establish and maintain an ethical, effective, inclusive and empathetic relationship with children and other stakeholders (e.g., parents) • Understand how to appreciate physical, mental and cultural diversity in children and adapt PAMPS practice accordingly
Coaching Practice	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Know how to conduct (comprehensive) needs analyses (assessments) for individual children (and/or teams) in order to design and deliver tailored coaching programmes, taking into account children needs and capabilities (in the context of wider programmes, curricula, policies and targets) • Understand how to select, design and justify appropriate pedagogy, practice and communication methods to facilitate the short, medium and long-term learning needs of children • Understand the core elements of multi skills or of their chosen sport(s) at the key stages of child development • Know how to deliver a series of coaching sessions in the context of medium term and long term planned programmes of practice and competition using a

	wide range of appropriate learning modes for children and coaching behaviours
Decision Making	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Understand how to conduct an informed analysis of own performance and of the performance of children towards ensuring continuous progress and improvement • Understand how to make good in-action and post-action decisions to increase the chances of reaching short-, mid- and long-term objectives • Apply knowledge of fundamentals of movement, fundamental movement skills and fundamental game skills to create practices that lead to short-term and long-term learning, including play • Apply knowledge of motor skill development for children and youth, including the stages/phases of skill development and the impact of growth and maturation
Coaching Review and Reflection	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Know how to conduct an insightful analysis of coaching practice to make informed judgements relating to the efficacy of the learning environment established • Reflect on their personal coaching knowledge, skills, attitudes, values, and practice, with the aim of continuously improving • Continuously build and engage with a network of coaches / coach developers to keep reviewing and building personal best-practices in coaching children, seeking supervised hands-on coaching contexts

Module Structure

Core Module	Inclusive Coaching / Safeguarding
Module Number	3
Core Module Aim	<p>The aim of the core module is to achieve:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Knowledge about inclusion at different levels in sport • Knowledge about the importance of positive and effective relationships (child, parents, club) in sport • Knowledge about the promotion of girls in sport • Knowledge about adapting the planning and implementation of sports programmes • Knowledge about potential dangers for children in sport • Knowledge about how to create a safe and preventative environment as a Youth Sport Coach
Module Description	<p>The Youth Sport Coach builds positive and effective relationships and works with a group of participants (children, parents, federations, and other levels). He or she takes responsibility for the realisation of the common and individual objectives, and to achieve the programme and club goals. Listening to the "voice" of each child is an important part of this process. Safeguarding and child protection must underpin the establishment of a safe environment for children in sport.</p> <p>The module will examine the theoretical basis of inclusion and safeguarding in sport and the importance for a positive and effective relationship between all participants and consider what they mean in practice when coaching children.</p> <p>The Youth Sport Coach should be able to meet all children in their program and facilitate participation and inclusion at all levels. The program should be tailored to the needs and developmental stage of each child.</p> <p>The organisational and social context of the programme, including the participants (children/parents/club/ ...) should be taken into account.</p>
Module Duration	30 hours (including 9 hours of Self-Directed Learning)
Facilities and Equipment	Seminar room and gym
Methodology	<p>Class based lectures / workshops to consider the knowledge / theories pertaining to inclusive coaching and safeguarding.</p> <p>The module will include field-based practical sessions during which coaches will be involved in experiencing practical coaching skills (peer-coaching), to examine the practical implications and application of the knowledge / theories, when coaching children.</p> <p>Self-directed learning as well as the completion and presentation of case studies will also be part of the module.</p>

Coaching Materials	Logbook / reflection book	
Suggested Readings	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • European Sport Coaching Framework • https://icoachkids.org/learn/inclusion/the-inclusion-spectrum • https://inclusiveskating.org/resources/i-coach-kids-study-guide-mooc-2-chapter-2-190621110212.pdf • Chapter 1: https://inclusiveskating.org/resources/icoach-kids-study-guide-mooc-2-introduction-190621110025.pdf • https://icoachkids.org/learn/parents/working-with-parents-in-sport • https://icoachkids.org/learn/coaching-girls/icoachgirls/guide1 • https://www.unicef.org.uk/sport-for-development/safeguarding-in-sport/ • International Safeguarding for Children in Sport • https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S2352250X16301415 • Jowett, S. (2017). Coaching effectiveness: the coach–athlete relationship at its heart, <i>Current Opinion in Psychology</i>, Volume 16. P 154-158, https://doi.org/10.1016/j.copsyc.2017.05.006 • Deci, E. L., & Ryan, R. M. (2008). Self-determination theory: A macrotheory of human motivation, development, and health. <i>Canadian Psychology / Psychologie canadienne</i>, 49(3), 182–185. https://doi.org/10.1037/a0012801 	
Evaluation	EduPASS Evaluation Tool for Youth Sport Coach Programmes	
Module structure <i>(each module requires AT LEAST 2 courses)</i>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Course 3.1: Exploring Inclusiveness in Sport <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ 3 h Lecture Teaching Units ○ 3 h Workshop/Practical Teaching Units ○ 2 h Self-Directed Working hours • Course 3.2: Effective Relationships <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ 3 h Lecture Teaching Units ○ 3 h Workshop/Practical Teaching Units ○ 2 h Self-Directed Working hours • Course 3.3: Adapting your Program – Coaching Girls in Sport <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ 3 h Lecture Teaching Units ○ 3 h Workshop/Practical Teaching Units ○ 2 h Self-Directed Working hours • Course 3.4: Safeguarding – Basics of Safe Environments <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ 3 h Lecture Teaching Units ○ 3 h Self-Directed Working hours 	
Learning outcomes <i>for Youth Sport Coaches</i>	The module will enable the Youth Sport Coach in training to build the following competencies (knowledge, skills, attitudes, values) which serve as a foundation when engaging with the children they coach:	
	Knowledge: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • About inclusion in general and specifically in sport • About the inclusion spectrum model in planning and implementing physical activity 	Skills: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • How to include all children through and in sport • Inclusive communication skills • Skills to promote cooperation • Didactic / pedagogical skills

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • About inclusive values and attitudes • About inclusive behaviour • About the influence of the social context • About inclusive communication • About the involvement of parents/clubs/ ... • About differentiated physical activity programmes • About safeguarding and preventative behaviour 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Motivational skills • Leadership skills • Active listening skills • Role modelling
	<p>Attitudes: <i>YSCs in training will have engaged in activities that foster development of the following attitudes when engaging with children they coach:</i></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Respecting children’s needs and interests • Enthusiasm • Cooperation • Motivation • Valuing individual differences • Empathy • Open-mindedness • Emotional intelligence • Sensitivity for diversity • Commitment to Safety and Well-being 	<p>Values: <i>YSCs in training will have engaged in activities that foster development of the following values when engaging with children they coach:</i></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Acceptance of social diversity • Compassion • Tolerance • Safety and Well-being • equality and treatment • Community Engagement • Respect • Empathy • Inclusion • Honesty
<p>Learning outcomes <i>for children/learners</i></p>	<p>The module will enable the Youth Sport Coach in training to support the children they coach to develop the following competencies (knowledge, skills, attitudes, values):</p>	
	<p>Knowledge:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • awareness about their interests & preferences • regarding basic motor development processes • fundamentals of social interaction 	<p>Skills:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Fun and enjoyment • Inclusive Communication skills • Cooperation skills • Motivation skills • Active Listening skills
	<p>Attitudes: <i>Children will have engaged in activities that foster development of the following attitudes when</i></p>	<p>Values: <i>Children will have engaged in activities that foster development of the following values when engaging</i></p>

	<p><i>engaging in PAMPS activities with other children:</i></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Respecting other children’s needs and interests • Enthusiasm • Creativity • Cooperation • Open-mindedness • Fun and enjoyment • Empathy • Patience 	<p><i>in PAMPS activities with other children:</i></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Respect • Fair play • Cooperation • Empathy • Inclusion • Honesty • Teamwork • Friendship • Positive Relationships
<p>Connection to other Core Module</p>	<p>Module 2: Principles of Coaching Module 6: Plan, Reflect and Learn</p>	

Course Structure

Course Title	Exploring Inclusiveness in Sport		
Course Number	3.1		
Course Description / Main Objective	<p>The Youth Sport Coach in training will be able to:</p> <p>The Youth Sport Coach uses their knowledge of the theoretical foundations of inclusion in youth sports to plan and conduct themselves in such a way that all children participate in the sports program. He chooses the games and movement tasks appropriately for each child and enables the achievement of individual goals.</p> <p>The Youth Sport Coach is aware of the importance of inclusive communication in their work. By using inclusive communication, they can build a positive and effective relationship with the children and parents.</p>		
Course Structure <i>(each module requires AT LEAST 2 Teaching Units)</i>	L / W	1.5 h	Teaching Unit 1: Inclusion and the different dimensions
	W / PE	1.5 h	Teaching Unit 2: Practical Implications of Applying the Inclusion Spectrum Model and the Differentiation
	L / W	1.5 h	Teaching Unit 3: 'Be inclusive'
	W / PE	1.5 h	Teaching Unit 4: Practical Implications of Applying Inclusive Behaviour to create an Inclusive Environment
	SDL	2 h	Teaching Unit 5: Complete the study guide for ICK and Essential Readings
Course Content <i>(examples of specific Course Content based on EduPASS LTT workshops are shared as separate slide decks)</i>	TU 1	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Classification and differentiation between inclusion and integration • PAMPS is there for all children • Inclusion Spectrum Model and the STEP Model for classifying and planning sports programmes to support and challenge each child individually 	
	TU 2	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Practical application and testing of the inclusion model for planning and implementing PAMPS programmes. Experience differentiation for the different starting points of the children through the STEP model 	
	TU 3	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The importance of the youth sports coach's own behaviour • What is meant by inclusive behaviour? What values are represented and how does inclusive language and communication work? • How can I behave inclusively? 	

	TU 4	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Practical application and testing of inclusive behaviour (language, positioning, choice of movement task and differentiation options for all children) through the teaching of sports programmes (PAMPS) and subsequent reflection on them
	TU 5	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • https://icoachkids.org/learn/inclusion/the-inclusion-spectrum • Study guide for ICK MOOC 2 Child-Centred Coaching & Physical Literacy, Chapter 2: Making Sport Inclusive - https://inclusiveskating.org/resources/i-coach-kids-study-guide-mooc-2-chapter-2-190621110212.pdf

Course Title	Effective Relationships		
Course Number	3.2		
Course Description / Main Objective	<p>The Youth Sport Coach in training will be able to:</p> <p>The youth sports coach recognises the importance of a positive and effective coach-child relationship and parent-coach relationship in their work. Through a good coach-child relationship, he can motivate the children to do sport and enable them to do sport in the long term.</p> <p>Developing a parent-friendly environment enables the involvement of parents in child-centred work, which can lead to a long-term active life.</p>		
Course Structure <i>(each module requires AT LEAST 2 Teaching Units)</i>	L / W	1.5 h	Teaching Unit 1: The Importance of Coach-Child-Relationship
	W / PE	3 h	Teaching Unit 2: Practical Implications of Applying the 3+1C Model (Jowett, 2017)
	L / W	1.5 h	Teaching Unit 3: Working with Parents in Sport
	SDL	2 h	Teaching Unit 4: Complete the study guide for ICK and Essential Readings
Course Content <i>(examples of specific Course Content based on EduPASS LTT workshops are shared as separate slide decks)</i>	TU 1	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Importance of the coach-child relationship basic needs for potential development – Self-Determination-Theory (SDT) (Deci & Ryan) Why children choose and stay in sport Why children stop participating in sport and what can be done about it 3+1C Model (Jowett, 2017) 	
	TU 2	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Practical application and testing of the 3+1C model in the implementation of and interaction with children and subsequent reflection on it 	
	TU 3	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Role of the parents in youth sport How do you create a parent-friendly environment? How do you involve parents positively? Role play – Develop and play out a parent-coach meeting 	
	TU 4	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Study guide for ICK MOOC 2: Child-Centred Coaching and Physical Literacy - https://inclusiveskating.org/resources/icoach-kids-study-guide-mooc-2-introduction-190621110025.pdf https://icoachkids.org/learn/parents/working-with-parents-in-sport 	

Course Title	Adapting your Program – Coaching Girls in Sport		
Course Number	3.3		
Course Description / Main Objective	<p>The Youth Sport Coach in training will be able to:</p> <p>The Youth Sport Coach can identify the key aspects that support girls' retention in physical activity and sport.</p> <p>The Youth Sport Coach will also be able to discuss the psychosocial needs of girls in sport and consider how they can meet these needs through their coaching practice to promote autonomy, confidence and belonging in girls in team and individual sports.</p> <p>The Youth Sport Coach understand the relationship between participation in physical activities, body image and maturation.</p> <p>The Youth Sport Coach can apply practical strategies to optimise coach-athlete relationships and support athlete voice during the coaching process.</p> <p>The Youth Sport Coach is aware of the importance of communication (coach to player and player to player) in engaging girls in sport.</p>		
Course Structure <i>(each module requires AT LEAST 2 Teaching Units)</i>	L / W	3 h	Teaching Unit 1: Coaching Girls in Sport
	W / PE	3 h	Teaching Unit 2: Practical Implications of Applying the 10 Girls in sport elements
	SDL	2 h	Teaching Unit 3: Complete the study guide for ICG
Course Content <i>(examples of specific Course Content based on EduPASS LTT workshops are shared as separate slide decks)</i>	TU 1	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Dropout And Engagement in Girls’ Sport and Physical Activity • Meeting the Psycho-Social Needs of Girls in Sport • Group Discussion: Coach-Athlete Relationship in Girls’ Sport • Body Image and Maturation • The Girls in Sport Elements: <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Focus on competence 2. Provide non-competitive activities 3. Provide high support 4. Offer a variety of activities and variations 5. Use role models 6. Promote friendships and social connections 7. Help coaches to understand girls’ needs 8. Create a positive, inclusive and welcoming environment 9. Provide girls only opportunities 10. Mitigate issues related to body image and act accordingly 	
	TU 2	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Practical application and creating a positive mastery motivational climate for girls and subsequent reflection on it 	
	TU 3	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • ICOACHGIRLS, (Re)Introducing Girls to Sport and Physical Activity: https://icoachkids.org/learn/coaching-girls/icoachgirls/guide1 	

Course Title	Safeguarding – Basics of Safe Environments		
Course Number	3.4		
Course Description / Main Objective	<p>The Youth Sport Coach in training will be able to:</p> <p>The Youth Sport Coach is responsible for ensuring that children do not put themselves in danger while playing sport. They know about the dangers and know what to do if something bad happens.</p> <p>The Youth Sport Coach is responsible for creating a safe environment as a preventative measure.</p>		
Course Structure <i>(each module requires AT LEAST 2 Teaching Units)</i>	L / W	3 h	Teaching Unit 1: Staying Safe as a Coach
	SDL	3 h	Teaching Unit 2: Essential Readings
Course Content <i>(examples of specific Course Content based on EduPASS LTT workshops are shared as separate slide decks)</i>	TU 1	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Safeguarding and Child Protection • Preventing and Taking Action against Child Abuse in Sport • Staying Safe as a Coach <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Sound Practice ○ Safety ○ Minimise Risk of Allegations 	
	TU 2	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • https://www.unicef.org.uk/sport-for-development/safeguarding-in-sport/ • International Safeguarding for Children in Sport 	